

This document is a subjective evaluation of openness of the following Open Science projects: Human Brain Project¹, Event Horizon Telescope ², Science Feedback³, Open Worm⁴, Safecast⁵, SenseBox⁶, Kiron⁷. For the evaluation we used 1 to 5 score (where 1 means 'low', and 5 means 'high') based on what exempt the projects meet 10 of the Vienna Open Science Principles⁸.

¹ <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/>

² <https://eventhorizontelescope.org/>

³ <https://sciencefeedback.co/>

⁴ <http://openworm.org/>

⁵ <https://safecast.org/>

⁶ <https://sensebox.de/en/>

⁷ <https://kiron.ngo/en/>

⁸ <https://viennaprinciples.org/>